

Unmasking Child Sex Trafficking: Education, Identification and Screening for California School Nurses

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Background

- Child Sex Trafficking (CST) is a form of human trafficking (HT) and child sexual abuse (CSA)
- A global public health threat
- Victims attend U.S. schools
- Average age of U.S. CST victims: 11-14
- California is home to one of the highest volumes of HT activity in the U.S.

Problem Statement

School nurses (SN):

- Often, only trusted healthcare providers in schools with frequent access to and interactions with students
- Are at the crux of identifying at-risk youth and victims of trafficking; within scope to screen
- Lack of appropriate HT education resulting in knowledge deficiencies and ineffective responses

Purpose

To develop an evidence-based HT educational model, inclusive of CST, tailored to CA SNs and sought their input on a validated CST screening tool for use in their practice settings.

Objectives:

- Assess SN's level of HT awareness
- Develop an educational module addressing knowledge gaps identified in pre-survey
- California School Nurses Organization State Board (CSNO) collaboration for pre-survey distribution
- Distribute educational module to interested pre-survey participants
- Elicit feedback on an evidence-based CST screening tool and distribute post-survey to assess the module's effect on SNs' awareness and attitudes

Methods

- Design:** Cross-sectional pre/post-test
- Setting:** Virtual (Bay Coast, Central Coast, Central Valley, Northern, San Diego-Imperial, & Southern sections)
- Sample:** CSNO members (active SNs & >18), Pre- (N=155) & Post-survey (N=50)
- Measurement Tool:** Awareness and Attitudes Assessment adapted from Donahue et al., 2019; Fraley & Aronowitz, 2021b; & Jordan et al., 2017

Results

Victim Encounter by SN

Pre-Survey (N=155): 14 (9.03%)
Post-Survey (N=50): 5 (10%)

SN Barriers to CST Identification

CST Screening Tool Appropriability

Discussion

- Gaps in SN awareness, perceptions, and knowledge of CST
- Interest in knowing more information/belief that knowing about and screening for CST is within the SN's role
- Structural and systematic barriers to CST identification faced by SNs
- Education alone is insufficient in addressing CST; a structural practice change is needed (i.e., CST screening tool, administrator support, HT district policies, and protocols)

Conceptual Framework

Adapted Socio-Ecological Model (SEM) for CST: A Lens for School Nurses

Clinical Implications

Future recommendations:

- Rollout CST screening tool
 - Measure: Tool usage, capacity, # identified cases, # actual reported cases
- Create SN working group to:
 - Develop standardized HT protocols and policies
 - Design CST-related curricula for SN credential programs
 - Collaborate with CSNO, CA Department of Education, CA Department of Public Health, and CA Commission on Teacher Credentialing

Limitations

- Limited timeframe for survey administration
- Convenience sample (majority women (>95%) and White (>70%))
- Risk for response bias
- The generalizability of findings may be limited beyond the project's environment due to the small sample size

Conclusion

- Complex nature of HT warrants sustainable training for SNs approached from a SEM lens
- SNs are in an optimal position to screen and it's within their scope

References

